

Automatic Timetable Generation

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Abstract—College timetabling with a large student population often relies on manual methods, where faculty members are responsible for creating schedules. This process is time-consuming and prone to errors, especially when dealing with multiple courses, subjects, and limited faculty resources. To address these challenges, this paper proposes a novel approach utilizing a Genetic Algorithm (GA). The GA is designed to optimize faculty scheduling by considering factors such as subject demands, faculty availability, and time slot constraints. The core of this research involves developing innovative GA operators that act at the element level to efficiently explore the solution space, defining fitness functions that evaluate the quality of generated timetables based on criteria such as faculty workload, class distribution, and time slot utilization, and optimizing GA parameters through rigorous testing to determine the optimal balance between crossover and mutation rates. The results demonstrate that the proposed GA-based approach significantly reduces the time required to generate timetables compared to manual methods. Moreover, the generated timetables exhibit higher accuracy, precision, and are free from human errors. This research highlights the potential of GA in automating and improving the college timetabling process.

Index Terms—*Genetic Algorithm, Timetable Scheduling, Constraints, Fitness chromosomes.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Timetabling is the task of creating a schedule while satisfying certain constraints [1]. It is a complex problem that involves allocating activities—such as academic sessions and lectures—to specific time slots and resources (e.g., instructors, students, and rooms) while adhering to predefined rules[2]. The primary challenge is to optimize the allocation process to avoid conflicts, ensure efficiency, and meet institutional requirements. Technology has significantly improved the efficiency and accuracy of various systems, including timetable management. Computers, being one of the greatest achievements of the last century, have become an essential tool in solving complex problems due to their speed, precision, security options, and ease of maintenance[1]. With advancements in computational methods, traditional approaches to scheduling are gradually being replaced by more efficient algorithms. One such method is the Genetic Algorithm (GA), which

is particularly effective for optimization problems. Genetic Algorithms work by searching a solution space to find the best possible outcome based on given constraints. In the context of timetabling, GA helps in efficiently resolving conflicts and clashes, ultimately leading to an optimized schedule[3]. Since timetabling is a real-world problem with immediate applications in various domains, using Genetic Algorithms can provide a feasible and automated solution. The objectives of this research are:

- 1) To define Genetic Algorithms and explain how they work.
- 2) To analyze timetable management and its inherent challenges.
- 3) To develop a prototype of an automated timetable scheduling system using Genetic Algorithms instead of the classical approach.

The current timetable system at Coventry University is considered adequate. Therefore, this research does not propose an alternative solution but rather focuses on exploring the efficiency of Genetic Algorithms in scheduling[4]. By utilizing Genetic Algorithms, timetable scheduling can be transformed into an optimization problem where the goal is to find the best possible schedule while maximizing a set of criteria. Since no universally efficient algorithm exists for solving such complex scheduling problems, Genetic Algorithms serve as an ideal solution to search through the solution space and generate optimized timetables[3].

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The study "Automatic Timetable Generator Using Genetic Algorithm" presents an in-depth methodology based on Genetic Algorithms. The approach involves encoding timetable data into chromosomes, initializing a feasible population, evaluating fitness using a scoring function (ranging from 0 to 1), and applying selection, crossover, and mutation to generate optimal schedules. This research highlights key advantages such as efficiency, scalability, and accuracy while also addressing challenges like computational overhead and the risk of local optima[1]. Similarly, the study "Time Table

Scheduling Using Genetic Algorithm” explores a GA-based approach to timetable scheduling, focusing on optimizing resource allocation and avoiding scheduling conflicts. The methodology includes defining scheduling parameters via an input configuration file, generating an initial population, performing fitness evaluation, applying selection, crossover, and mutation, and incorporating a repair strategy to ensure feasibility. The research emphasizes benefits such as automation, conflict resolution, scalability, and optimization, while also acknowledging challenges like computational cost, sensitivity to parameter settings, and the risk of convergence to local optima [3]. Several researchers have analyzed the increasing complexity of timetabling problems, particularly in higher secondary schools and universities, where different types of class structures make scheduling more challenging. Initially, timetable scheduling was primarily applied in schools, where simple class structures allowed classical methods like linear and integer programming to be effective. However, as institutions with more complex scheduling needs emerged, classical methods became insufficient, leading to the exploration of metaheuristic approaches such as Genetic Algorithms[4]. The key modules involved in the scheduling process, which are fundamental for efficient timetable generation. These include:

- Data Encoding and Decoding – Converting scheduling constraints and information into a computationally processable form.
- Initial Population – Generating a set of potential timetable solutions.
- Evaluation of Population – Scoring each solution based on constraint satisfaction.
- Crossover Evolution – Combining elements of parent solutions to create new schedules.
- Mutation – Introducing small changes to enhance diversity and avoid local optima.
- New Population Generation – Creating a refined set of solutions for the next iteration.

Apart from Genetic Algorithms, researchers have explored alternative optimization techniques for timetable scheduling. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) has been introduced as an effective approach for solving university course timetabling problems. The study explains how PSO mimics the collective movement of birds and fish swarms to find an optimal timetable arrangement. The PSO-based scheduling system follows these key steps: Initialization: A set of particles (potential timetable solutions) is randomly generated, each representing a possible schedule.

Fitness Function: Each particle is evaluated based on constraints such as avoiding overlapping classes, ensuring room and instructor availability, and minimizing unnecessary gaps between classes [5].

Comparison of Timetable Scheduling Algorithms

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF TIMETABLE SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS

Algorithm	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages
Genetic Algorithm (GA)	Heuristic-based selection algorithm.	Handles complex problems.	Computationally expensive.
Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)	Swarm intelligence-based optimization.	Fast convergence.	Less effective in complex spaces.
Tabu Search	Memory-based optimization avoiding repetitions.	Efficient for constrained problems.	May get stuck in cycles.
Simulated Annealing (SA)	Inspired by annealing in metallurgy.	Escapes local minima effectively.	Parameter tuning is critical.

III. METHODOLOGY

Architecture of Automatic Timetable Generation using Genetic Algorithm:

Fig. 1. Automatic Timetable Architecture

Proposed System Workflow:

1) Input Data:

- Professor: Data describes the name of lecturers along with their identification number.
- Subject: Data describes the name of courses in the current term.
- Room: Data describes the room number and their capacity.
- Time intervals: It indicates starting time along with duration of a lecture.

2) Hard Constraints:

- A student should have only one class at a Time.
- A Teacher should have only one class at a time.
- A room should be booked only for one class at a time.
- Some classes require classes to have particular equipment. For example, audio visual equipment, projectors etc.

3) Soft Constraints:

- Courses must be eventually distributed.
- Students should not have any free time between two classes on a day.
- Scheduling of teachers should be well spread over the week.

Timetable Generation Process:

- Algorithm: The system would use a chosen algorithm (e.g., Genetic Algorithm) to generate the timetable.
- Constraints: The algorithm would consider various constraints:
 - Room Capacity: Ensure classes are scheduled in rooms with sufficient capacity.
 - Lecturer Availability: Ensure lecturers are not assigned to multiple classes simultaneously.
 - Room Availability: Ensure rooms are not double-booked.
 - Day Time Slot Availability: Ensure no clashes in the schedule.
 - Course Prerequisites: Ensure courses are scheduled in the correct order.

Output :

Timetable Generation: Once the algorithm generates a feasible timetable, it would be stored in the Timetable Table.

Visualization: The system could then generate visual representations of the timetable, such as:

- Class Schedule: A schedule for each class, showing the assigned room, time slot, and lecturer.
- Lecturer Schedule: A schedule for each lecturer, showing their assigned classes and times.
- Room Schedule: A schedule for each room, showing the classes assigned to that room.

Algorithm:

- 1) Create a population of objects (creatures) //Initialization
- 2) Evaluate the fitness of each object //analyzing
- 3) While the population is not fit enough //Fitness check
- 4) Delete all unfit objects //Removing unfit objects
- 5) While population size \leq max: //size check
- 6) Select two best populations
- 7) Create new objects
- 8) Random mutations
- 9) Evaluate and place in population //breeding

Flow of Genetic Algorithm

- 1) **Data encoding and decoding:** Data encoding is the first step before starting Genetic Algorithm. It transforms a solution into a chromosome to get a simple value, like a string. It is used to improve speed of the algorithm.

Fig. 2. Flow of Genetic Algorithm

- 2) **Initial population:** It is the first step in GA. It consists of creating a number of random individuals using hard constraints. The population choice depends on the needs of the user.
- 3) **Evaluation of population:** The evaluation of the population is the heart of the Genetic Algorithm. this step evaluate which solution is better than other using a fitness function
- 4) **Fitness Function:** The fitness can be given using a range between 0 and 1, where 1 is estimated as the best solution of the population.

$$F(\mathbf{X}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \cdot W}{t}$$

Where, x = timetable under evaluation process. w = number of Constraints. t = total fitness value

- 5) **Crossover Evolution:** The crossover evolution is a method used for the creation of a new population, based on older population. The simple crossover evolution uses two chromosomes and permit to create X new chromosomes. It consists of splitting the two chromosomes in parts and creating new chromosomes using different parts
- 6) **Mutation:** Mutation is used to get the algorithm moving. It consists of changing the values of a gene randomly, resulting in a new unexpected solution. These solutions offer a new point of view for the fitness function.

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 3. Timetable Generation - Initial Performance Analysis

A. Key Observations

- **Room Conflict:** Setting the penalty to **0.24** achieved **perfect fitness (1.0)** with **zero violations**.
- **Penalty Weights:** Higher penalty weights generally resulted in **fewer violations**.
- **Teacher Workload:** A setting of **0.086** produced a **high score (0.87)** with only **2 violations**.
- **Course Repetition:** A setting of **0.07** resulted in the **lowest score (0.52)** with **8 violations**.
- **Generation Count:** It does not directly correlate with the **fitness score**, indicating that other factors influence convergence.

B. Key Observations

Preliminary Evaluation: The initial analysis of timetable generation revealed **significant variations** in fitness scores and violations.

Penalty Impact: Lower penalty values resulted in **higher violations**, indicating the need for fine-tuning.

Fitness Score Trends: Early experiments show that **penalty weight adjustments** significantly impact overall fitness.

Fig. 4. Timetable Generation Results - Analysis of Penalty Weights and Fitness Score

Fig. 5. Optimization Strategies - Effect of Penalty Weights on Fitness

C. Key Findings for Fig 5

- **Best Overall:** Setting the **Room Conflict penalty to 0.24** achieved **perfect fitness (1.0)** with zero violations.
- **Efficiency:** A **Room Conflict setting of 0.2** reached a good solution (**0.75 fitness**) in just **104 generations**, showing **faster convergence**.
- **Balanced Approach:** **Teacher Workload of 0.086** produced **excellent results (0.87 fitness)** with minimal violations.
- **Recommendation:** Increasing **Room Conflict penalties** appears to be the **most effective strategy** for optimizing timetable generation.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this study, we have successfully implemented the Automatic Timetable Generation system using a Genetic Algorithm, Utilizing a real-time database from our institution. The system dynamically processes actual scheduling data, including faculty availability, subject constraints, and classroom allocations, ensuring an optimized and conflict-free timetable. Our approach demonstrates that integrating real-time data with Genetic Algorithms significantly improves the adaptability and accuracy of timetable scheduling.

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